

ASPECTS OF USING INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION MEANS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract: All higher education institutions in Uzbekistan need to improve the methodology of teaching information technology to future primary school teachers in the new digital conditions. In this regard, the importance of students in the educational process, their professional tasks in the entire labor market, and this, in turn, led to an increase in the tendency to form and develop professional communicative competences through information and communication technologies. This article describes the methods of forming the competence of future elementary school teachers in the use of information and communication tools.

Key words: technology, competence, communicative, information and communication technologies, synchronous and asynchronous multimedia.

Introduction:

All higher education institutions in Uzbekistan need to improve the methodology of teaching information technologies to future primary school teachers in the new digital conditions. Therefore, the importance of students in the educational process, their professional tasks in the entire labor market, and this, in turn, led to an increase in the tendency to form and develop professional communicative competences with information and communication tools. The educational policy of each higher education institution should be aimed at solving the problem of training competitive specialists who are socially protected, adapted to constantly changing conditions and have formed professional communicative competence.

In the early stages of development, programs for the use of information and communication technologies in the educational process were developed, opinions about their use in the educational process were positively and critically revised, methodological bases for their use in the educational process was created. Proposals that it is possible to organize full education in the course of the lesson without the teacher interfering in the lesson only with information and communication tools are rejected. However, information and communication tools not only freed teachers from routine, traditional tasks, but also placed tasks related to programming, teaching materials, and technical

coordination. In order for information and communication tools to be a powerful factor in the effectiveness of the didactic process, they should correspond to the goal-content program of this process and help to implement the main functions of pedagogical management. Therefore, in order to improve the methodology of teaching information technology to future elementary teachers in the context of digitization in the educational process, the teacher must know the right balance between technology tools, teaching methods and approaches.

Most importantly, the use of information and communication tools in education develops students' professional communicative competence, the ability to develop research skills, intellectual competence to develop independence, creative thinking, cognitive activity, thinking, essay writing and checking skills. In the conditions of digitization, future primary school teachers were distinguished by the rapid development of research in areas where it is possible to improve the methodology of information technology education. Later, one of several Uzbek scientists, R. J. Ishmuhamedov, put forward the opinion that it is better to use information and communication technologies in primary classes, to perform the tasks of consultants, partners, and to use them for educational purposes.

Thus, in the conditions of digitization, it is necessary to improve the methodology of teaching information technology to future primary school teachers, to develop programs to support the use of information and communication tools for teaching in primary school, training and testing it is necessary to develop programs exit, development of computer courses, distance learning, we can see that the use of internet in classrooms is effective.

In the conditions of digitalization, the future primary class creates new opportunities for teachers to improve the teaching methods of information media. Using the Internet allows you to conduct online classes in real time.

Learning on the basis of information and communication tools in primary education consists in developing students' professional communication skills, organizing live communication and activities on computer networks. Technologies, conditions for digitalization, and the improvement of the methodology of information technology education for future primary school teachers will lead to its informatization. On the basis of data, a personal computer, tens and hundreds of gigabytes of optical disks that allow storing the contents of entire libraries in a compact form, optical fiber communication channels, video-text communication systems, methods of presenting information and knowledge, e-mail systems, etc.

All technologies ensure the creation of a highly automated information environment and theoretically allow arbitrary access. Accordingly, education should ensure the formation of new competencies necessary for people to live in the new information environment of life, including education in the conditions of widespread use of modern information technologies, as well as understanding of the new integrated world and information outlook.

For future elementary school teachers in conditions of improved interactive (information-search, information-analytic, information-communicative, information-reflexive, information-technological, information-functional, information-professional) digitization with synchronous and asynchronous multimedia tools improvement of information technology teaching methodology.

The methodology of forming the competence of future elementary school teachers in the use of information and communication tools is usually related to the combination of theoretical knowledge and practical skills. This may include: the integration of technology in education. ICT training courses: There is a need to provide specific ICT courses to ensure that teachers are familiar with various tools, software and platforms. Hands-On campaign. Conducting hands-on training, creating lesson plans, and conducting interactive activities where prospective teachers can gain hands-on experience using educational technologies.

Pedagogical integration: Teaching the seamless integration of technology into lesson plans, ensuring its further enhancement. Collaborative Learning: Encourage collaborative projects that involve the use of communication tools, teamwork, and effective use of collaborative platforms. Continuous professional development: building an ideology of continuous learning, encouraging teachers to stay up-to-date on emerging technologies and pedagogical strategies. Assessment Strategies: Teaching Teachers to Assess Students' Digital Literacy Skills and Use Formative and Summative Assessment Technologies.

Flexibility: Instilling flexibility allows teachers to adopt emerging technologies and incorporate them into teaching methods. Reflective practice. Encourage reflective practice in which teachers assess the impact of technology on student learning and adapt their instruction accordingly. Future elementary school teachers can develop strong competence in the effective use of information and communication tools in the classroom by using a comprehensive approach that combines theory, practical application, and ongoing professional development.

Also, a number of researchers say that the content of information competence includes two elements: single basic knowledge and skills for professionals of a voluntary profession, and profession-oriented, special knowledge and skills for a certain profession. According to professional information competence includes the basic knowledge and skills common to all computer users, as well as professionally oriented knowledge and skills that ensure professional mobility and high competitiveness of a person in professional activities.

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